

2008 Summary Report for the Nantucket Spider Biodiversity Inventory

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Project Summary

We have identified 258 species of spider on Nantucket, Tuckernuck, and Muskeget Islands (Table 1). There are an additional 38 “morphological” species that may increase the total count after they have been fully identified. Based on our sampling effort, we estimate that we have identified one half to two thirds of the total species on the islands.

In 2008, most collecting on Nantucket was done in the Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve as part of Mckenna-Foster’s Master’s thesis work (report to be submitted to the Nantucket Land Bank, Nantucket Land Council and NBI May 2009). We also performed detailed population studies of the Northern Black Widow (*Latrodectus variolus*) and the Red-legged Purseweb Spider (*Sphodros rufipes*) on Tuckernuck Island. During the summer, we accepted casual collections from the public as well as those from public collecting events held at the Maria Mitchell Natural Science Museum and on Tuckernuck Island (through the Tuckernuck Land Trust (TLT)).

Table 1. Collection statistics for 2008.

	Species Count	Specimen Count
Named	258	3,576
Morphological	38	159
Unidentifiable	-	2,505
Totals	-	6,240
Estimated in collection	~ 285	-
Estimated on Islands	~ 420 - 560	-

Current Outreach Projects

Our spider collecting effort up to this point (2006-2008) has included 48 collectors and several educational events each summer. These events range from programs with local schools to group collecting trips. We have submitted an abstract for an 18 minute presentation on the spider work to be given at the Invertebrates in Education and Conservation Conference in July 2009 (last page). The Electronic Field Guide to Spiders of Nantucket is being assembled and uploaded to a server this summer (with generous help from the University of Massachusetts). We will print a simple pamphlet of Common Spiders of Tuckernuck for the TLT Field Station. We will adapt the pamphlet to make a version for Nantucket Island and copies will be distributed to the UMass Field Station, Maria Mitchell Association Natural Science Library, and any other facilities that want a copy.

Current and Future Projects

We continue to identify and sort spiders. Since 2007, we have identified 40 of the 48 unidentified Linyphiidae. Several of these are interesting because they either represent a major range extension or are relatively rare species (whether due to global under-sampling or actual rarity is unclear usually). There are also several rare species representing the Theridiidae (cobweb spiders). This is in addition to the purseweb spiders (*Sphodros rufipes* and *Sphodros niger*) and northern black widow (*Latrodectus variolus*). These projects are direct descendents of the original species survey.

In terms of species lists for habitats, we have compiled the most accurate list for sandplain grassland and coastal heathland habitat (>106 species from 2,079 specimens, 11% of total collection). Because this list is so complete, in 2009, we will use it to perform one of the first tests of a Rapid Assessment Protocol for Spiders and Millipedes in a temperate region. This project will be a collaborative effort with current research in the forests of Panama and in the upper Midwest through the University of Wisconsin-Green Bay and the Chicago Field Museum.

We are dividing the entire collection into voucher collections for the Maria Mitchell Natural Science Museum and the Museum for Comparative Zoology. An additional voucher collection of the Linyphiidae will be sent to Dr. Michael Draney at the University of Wisconsin-Green Bay. We expect this to be complete by October 2009. Soon after, we hope to submit a report to NBI that describes the collection as a whole and describes new state and county records. A version of this document will be submitted for publication in the *Journal of Arachnology*. Additional planned publications include:

1. A comparison of species between the current collection and the historical James Emerton collection.
2. A range extension of a rarely collected Linyphiid that lives with ants and seems to be common on Nantucket.
3. A description of behaviors and natural history for the northern black widows on Tuckernuck.

Below is the abstract submitted for the Invertebrates in Education and Conservation Conference, July and August 2009, Arizona:

Documenting Nantucket Island's Spider Diversity Using Citizen Science
Andrew Mckenna-Foster and Cheryl Beaton

In 2006, depending entirely on inexperienced volunteers, we initiated a survey of spiders on Nantucket Island, Massachusetts funded by the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative. We collected as many species as possible using quantitatively comparable methods. We used the project as an educational opportunity for adults and children and harnessed their enthusiasm to collect specimens. Activities included collecting excursions, casual collecting events, spider "walks" aimed at children, live spider museum exhibits, and local media coverage for interesting finds. The outcome is a species list of the island's spider fauna (250 species), permanent live spider exhibits in the museum, and an online electronic field guide to common species.